

ARTICLES

INITIAL TEACHER TRAINING THROUGH PIBID: EXPERIENCES IN SCHOOLS IN THE MUNICIPALITY OF SÃO RAIMUNDO NONATO-PI¹

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ABSTRACT: This article aims to investigate the pedagogical experiences of undergraduate physics students in the Institutional Program for Teaching Initiation Scholarships (PIBID) at the Federal Institute of Education of Piauí (IFPI) between 2018 and 2020 in the municipality of São Raimundo Nonato, in the state of Piauí. The study discusses the experience of the Program and its implications for the initial training of physics teachers; it analyzes the importance of the Program in schools and the impacts of its actions in public schools in the municipality, *where the activities took place*. The experiences deal with the implementation of PIBID in three public schools in the municipality. Thus, the results show that it has established itself as a policy for the initial training of teachers and a means of improving teaching and pedagogical practices. It is concluded that the work of scholarship students and supervisors of the pedagogical axes contributed to the training of future physics teachers.

KEYWORDS: Physics teaching. Physics degree. Public school. High school.

FORMAÇÃO INICIAL DE PROFESSORES ATRAVÉS DO PIBID: EXPERIÊNCIAS EM ESCOLAS DO MUNICÍPIO DE SÃO RAIMUNDO NONATO-PI

RESUMO: O artigo objetiva investigar as experiências pedagógicas vivenciadas pelos estudantes de Licenciatura em física no Programa Institucional de Bolsas de Iniciação à Docência-PIBID do Instituto Federal de Educação do Piauí

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durante os anos de 2018 a 2020, no município de São Raimundo Nonato, no estado do Piauí. O estudo discute a experiência do Programa e suas implicações na formação inicial dos professores de Física; analisa a importância do Programa nas escolas e os impactos das ações nas escolas públicas do município, locus das atividades. As experiências versam sobre a implantação e implementação do PIBID em 03 escolas públicas do município. Assim, os resultados mostram que o mesmo se firma como uma política de formação inicial de professores e um meio de aprimoramento das práticas docentes e pedagógicas. Conclui-se que o trabalho de atuação dos estudantes bolsistas e dos supervisores dos eixos pedagógicos trouxe contribui para a formação dos futuros professores de Física.

PALAVRAS-CHAVE: Ensino de Física. Licenciatura em Física. Escola pública. Ensino médio.

Introduction

Studies show that a third world nation, such as Brazil, when it does not have priority interests in building a quality educational system, makes teaching, such a noble position, devalued and without social values. Furthermore, it fails to recognize the role of professional educators as fundamental to the ethical and moral development and education of children, adolescents, and young people, who in the future will assume social positions to serve society, where their ethics, character, and intellectual level are developed, mainly in the country's basic education schools. (GATTI; BARRETTO, 2009).

As demonstrated by Law No. 12,772, dated December 28, 2012, the low salaries of teachers in Brazil and the teaching career plan, which offers no incentives to join the profession, directly influence the career choices of young people, especially those who aspire to join the federal education network, few of whom are attracted to teaching in basic, technical, and technological education (EBTT). This reality has been a cause for concern for decades, as revealed by researchers and scholars on the subject, with regard to education for the population that accesses the public school system in the Brazilian context. (ARROYO, 1992; ALVES; PIMENTEL, 2015; BARBOSA, 2012).

According to Candau (2002) and Oliveira and Martins (2007), the Brazilian educational system still has a long way to go in terms of quality social and educational policies in all regions of the country. It is noticeable in poorer regions that cultural decline is reflected in schools, directly influencing the teaching and learning process of students, as well as the low motivation of educators at various levels of education in state capitals and municipalities. Thus, we can foresee a clear deconstruction of public education, where low salaries, social problems, and other issues accentuate the serious social problem of the devaluation of the teaching profession and the lack of investment in public policies for schools.

There is a shortage of pencils and sometimes even shoes. Thirty (or forty?) in each classroom. New blackboards, worn blackboards. Half-broken desks. The principal is concerned with renovating the building, guiding and supervising teachers, has a pile of papers to sign, and is honored at graduation. There are other people at the school: cooks, janitors, secretaries, inspectors. Salaries are low. Life is hard. But school is a place for teaching and learning (FONTANA; CRUZ, 1997, p. 3).

Teaching with a view to ensuring quality education is fundamental to guaranteeing access to knowledge, in order to reduce social inequalities in the country, in the pursuit of economic and social development. Spreading knowledge in its various fields throughout the world is so noble and important that we can shape future brilliant minds in the intellectual development of students, leading to the advancement of the nation alongside first world nations.

For educator Paulo Freire (1921-1997), honorably recognized as the patron of education in Brazil, "education changes people, and people change the world" (FREIRE, 1987, p. 87). He emphasizes that this change involves a transformation in the ways educators think and act, adding that "teaching is not transferring knowledge, but creating the possibilities for its production or construction. Those who teach learn to teach, and those who learn teach as they learn" (FREIRE, 2014, p. 22).

Currently in Brazil, we have programs and projects to promote and support teaching, research, and extension, which aim to improve the quality of higher education in Brazil. The Institutional Program for Teaching Initiation Scholarships (PIBID) is fundamental as a continuing policy for investments in the initial training of

teachers in higher education centers in Brazil (RAUSCH; FRANTZ, 2013). The program offers teaching initiation scholarships, aimed at students in face-to-face courses focused on internship activities in public schools. Thus, undergraduate students commit themselves to teaching with values acquired during their academic career and teaching internship while studying at public schools.

The main objective of PIBID is to promote exchange and links between future teachers in basic education and public education institutions in Brazil. It consists of a "bridge" between higher education (through teaching degree courses) and municipal, state, and federal schools in Brazil (AMBROSETTI et al., 2013), where novice and experienced teachers exchange knowledge and insights essential for the training of future professionals.

In this sense, this article presents some of the experiences of teachers and academics from the Federal Institute of Education, Science, and Technology of Piauí, São Raimundo Nonato Campus-IFPI/CASRN, in the development of activities proposed by PIBID, which aims to investigate the pedagogical experiences and practices experienced by students of the Physics Degree program between 2018 and 2020, in the municipality of São Raimundo Nonato, in the state of Piauí. Specifically, it discusses the experience of the Program from 2018 to 2020 and its implications for the initial training of physics teachers, and analyzes the importance of PIBID/IFPI/CASRN in schools and the impacts of actions in public schools in the municipality of São Raimundo Nonato-PI, the locus of the activities.

To this end, this paper is organized according to the motivations presented in the introduction (section 1). In section 2, we report on the implementation and development of PIBID actions at the IFPI São Raimundo Nonato Campus, followed by a subsection in which we present the views of scholarship recipients regarding the Program's contributions to the initial training of science teachers, and the three pedagogical axes related to the schools that received PIBID activities. The results are presented and discussed in section 3 (results and discussions), and section 4 presents the final conclusions of the work, developed in public schools selected by the PIBID program via public notice by the pedagogical center supervisors and the students collaborating on this work under the supervision of the PIBID/IFPI/CASRN area coordinator.

1 Implementation of PIBID at IFPI *Campus* São Raimundo Nonato-PI: A brief history of the consolidation of the Program

The PIBID selection public notice published by the Dean of Education-PROEN/IFPI, under No. 94 of June 15, 2018, contained vacancies for students from the São Raimundo Nonato Campus for the Bachelor's Degree in Physics. The selection was based on an analysis of *the student's curriculum* and a motivational essay, as a means of understanding the student's intellectual abilities and their intentions and motivations for participating in the Program. The selected candidates were awarded a PIBID scholarship by the pedagogical organization in stages of teaching practice development (see Fig. 1).

At the institution, the Program was organized into five areas that corresponded to the systematization of actions over the two years of implementation. They were named: AREA I: IFPI/CASRN - Public basic education networks in Piauí; AREA II: IFPI/CASRN - Pedagogical practices; and AREA III: Research as a formative principle, all with a workload of 160 hours of activities, and AXIS IV entitled: Institutional Seminar of the Institutional Program for Teaching Initiation Scholarships, corresponding to 20 hours of research socialization activities in the field of teaching and extension. All activities were planned and carried out at the

in order to achieve the Program's objectives, as we will see below in the discussion of some of the results presented in this article.

PIBID teaching practices were developed in the following schools: Centro de Ensino Médio de Tempo Integral Moderna-CETI, Unidade Escolar Edith Nobre de Castro, and CEEP-Gercilio de Castro Macedo, located in the municipality of São Raimundo Nonato, in the state of Piauí. During the development of the PIBID-IFPI-Physics subproject, the scholarship recipients (students in the Physics Degree program) made several visits to the centers involved in the subproject¹. Thus, for better control of the activities developed, a frequency was established, whereby at each visit to the center, the scholarship recipients recorded their attendance and the supervisors wrote a summary of the activities performed by each of them.

During the course of the work, there were scholarship recipients who were unable to comply with the Program's rules for personal and academic reasons, such as dropping a subject and/or the course. It should be noted that, according to the rules of the call for applications, as established, failure to comply with the items already mentioned would result in the scholarship recipients being dismissed. As there were cases of suspension/cancellation of scholarships, a Union Collection Guide (GRU) was generated in a document for the unified tax in the amount of the scholarships paid in the months in which the student did not participate and/or abandoned the Program, for not complying with their established obligations, as specified in the notice presented.

The PIBID-IFPI/CASRN began with general teaching and educational training (Studies on the Law of Guidelines and Bases for National Education-LDB Law 9.394/96) in 60 hours of classroom activities with all students enrolled in the IFPI/CASRN Physics Degree course. The EIXO-I course was taught by an educator, a specialist professor from *the Campus*, with the aim of discussing the legal aspects of Brazilian education, with an emphasis on guidelines and foundations, anchored in the following discursive themes: Education; principles and purposes of National Education; the right to Education and the duty to Educate; private initiative; organization of National Education; responsibilities of the Union, States, and Municipalities; responsibilities of educational establishments and teachers; Levels and Modalities of Education and Teaching; Basic and Higher Education.

The PIBID/IFPI/CASRN team presented the pedagogical AXES of the Program to the selected students and administrators of the aforementioned schools, developed the established practices, and prepared an activity monitoring report containing important information about the reality of the students and public schools in the municipality. These results, directly related to the reality of the students and schools, confirm that the public institutional program meets the training needs of students in the local community, presenting the reality of the municipality's schools in the various activities developed during the term of the PIBID/IFPI/CASRN Scholarship.

According to the management team of the schools involved, the supervisors of the teaching centers, and the students of the Physics Degree course - IFPI/CASRN, PIBID was fundamental for improving the quality of physics teaching and for the initial training of physics teachers at IFPI, as each stage defined was related to teaching, research, and extension, constituting a source of data described according to the following axes:

- Stage I. Training in Teaching Initiation

¹ Refers to the teaching degree course to which the Program is linked at the educational institution.

- Stage II. Observation of the School Environment
- Stage III. Technical Visit to the centers by those involved in PIBID/IFPI/CASRN
- Stage IV. Disciplinary and Interdisciplinary Activities
- Stages V and VI. Research as a formative principle
- Stage VII - Seminars to disseminate the results obtained by the PIBID/IFPI/CASRN initiative

The following table shows the schedule used in the execution of activities during the term of the PIBID/IFPI/CASRN scholarship and activities carried out each month of the subproject's execution in the pedagogical axis of public schools in the municipality of São Raimundo Nonato.

TABLE 01: Schedule of activities for the duration of the PIBID/IFPI/CASRN scholarship in the period 2018-2020

CRONOGRAMA DE ATIVIDADE: (PIBID/IFPI/CASRN)																		
ANO	2018	2018	2018	2018	2018	2019	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020	2021	
MESES	AGO	SET	OUT	NOV	DEZ	JAN	FEV	MAR	ABR	MAI	JUN	JUL	AGO	SET	OUT	NOV	DEZ	JAN
ATIVIDADE 01	X	X	X															
ATIVIDADE 02			X	X	X	X	X	X	X									
ATIVIDADE 03							X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X				
ATIVIDADE 04	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
ATIVIDADE 05	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

SOURCE: PIBID/IFPI/CASRN report.

The technical visit aimed to present the Program and clarify its objectives and goals to educational institutions by presenting the schedule of activities for PIBID 2018/2020 and the activity plan, developed around the pedagogical practices at the following schools: CEEP-Gercilio De Castro Macedo, Edith Nobre School Unit, and Moderna Full-Time High School Center (CETI). The school building (physical structure), together with its pedagogical and curricular organization, the institution's space in terms of technical maintenance and safety, are determining factors in the lives of students and future teachers who seek to develop character, values, and moral and ethical principles. A well-managed and well-organized school will enable students to use the knowledge they have learned effectively, so that it can be applied for the benefit of society and a better reality for all (RIBEIRO, 2004).

Thus, at the end of the visit, the scholarship recipients prepared and presented reports containing information resulting from their observations, discussions with supervisors, and readings of scientific articles, in which they shared the positive and negative aspects of the school environment. These points were addressed in meetings at IFPI/CASRN, in meetings and seminars between the centers and in schools with the school administrators, with the aim of identifying shortcomings and thus suggesting a better school environment for students enrolled in schools with pedagogical axes (BELTRAME; MOURA, 2009). Concerns about the teaching and learning process in schools were addressed through the analysis of data collected by scholarship recipients for inductive field research.

The scholarship recipients presented a series of seminars to present their research in pedagogical debates on studies and research in the areas of axes I, II, and III, respectively: public basic education networks in Piauí; pedagogical practices; and research as a formative principle. The consolidation of axis IV, the

The scientific seminars were intended not only to present the results, but also to prepare students in the Physics Degree program for public speaking and to discuss the topics studied and raised in the research.

The seminar on bullying was an important experience in terms of interdisciplinary practices in the pedagogical axis of the Program, in which groups of scholarship students developed a quantitative research script for school students on the topic. Also noteworthy are the Science Fairs, which sought to promote a scientific culture in schools through the development and presentation of studies and experiments by students.

The communication of the scholarship recipients during the presentation of these seminar cycles to the academic community of IFPI/CASRN, the self-criticism and evaluation of the supervisors and area coordinator of the Program were judged positively by the participants, and the issues were presented to the public with the aim of informing and presenting the reality of public schools in the municipality. This close relationship between education and teacher training, from Freire's perspective, corroborates reflections in the field of training, given that

- (1) training, whether initial or continuing, requires a context of problematization of reality;
- (2) listening as the basis for dialogue is both a practice and an indispensable element in the training process;
- (3) time is a fundamental dimension for the materiality of policies and educational intentionality;
- (4) dialogical relationship is an expression of the theory-practice relationship that translates the concreteness of a training concept. (SANTIAGO; BATISTA NETO, 201, p. 9).

Therefore, it is clear that there was evidence of teaching practices developed at PIBID/IFPI/CASRN based on Freirean thinking, built through the experience of the Seminar as a pedagogical and dialogical device, which brought future physics teachers into contact with the dynamics and reality of public schools, in the problematization and deepening of pedagogical relationships between students and teachers in basic education.

1.1 Contributions of PIBID to the initial training of science teachers in the view of physics undergraduates

After weekly meetings lasting two hours during the PIBID/IFPI/CASRN scholarship period, the topics were discussed in the form of experiences gained at science seminars and fairs, as mentioned above. In the studies and articles produced by PIBID/IFPI/CASRN scholarship students, their various classroom activities revealed their experiences in their future workplace between August 2018 and January 2020. During the weekly meetings, the groups of students involved in the pedagogical axes of the Program presented their experiences in scientific seminars and conducted literature research as a methodological approach to teaching Physics, as well as the importance of PIBID/IFPI/CASRN.

The results presented by the students were based on Freire's philosophical approach, the development of their career plans in basic education teaching in schools in the municipality of São Raimundo Nonato-Piauí, as well as various approaches to the reality of the public schools selected by the Program. For this work, we will emphasize the seminar on bullying and the Science Fair held during the interdisciplinary practices in each pedagogical axis of the Program, where the discussions will be presented in sections

111 1.1.2 and 1.1.3 below.

1.1.1 Pedagogical focus: Modern Full-Time Secondary School

First, a series of lectures on bullying was held with the students, followed by a diagnostic survey, in which 89 printed questionnaires were administered to students in the 3rd year of high school.

medium with the aim of investigating the occurrence or non-occurrence of bullying situations and what students and families know about the subject. The questionnaire sought to find out whether students talk to their parents about what they experience in the classroom; how families participate in school life; whether students feel comfortable talking about this subject at school and with their families; whether they have ever suffered any type of bullying at school and, if so, what type and how they react when they witness such situations at school.

Thus, the students' experiences in the public education environment were analyzed, and an understanding of the reality of public schools in the municipality of São Raimundo Nonato and the students' family life was established. Therefore, it is not only the school's duty to educate, but the family is also fundamental in this process and in the student's development, in their construction of ethical and moral knowledge to assume future social positions, which they acquired in a good study environment, without bullying in the construction of their ethical and moral formation process in the school of the pedagogical axis of the municipality of São Raimundo Nonato.

The responses showed that the majority of students, about 70.79%, talk to their parents about what they experience in the classroom. It can be observed, then, that the majority of students talk to their parents about their classroom experiences, but it cannot be ruled out that this is a high number, even though the minority answered no.

With regard to family participation in school, of the students interviewed, 42.70% of family members are absent from school and 57.30% are present. These data lead to questioning and understanding the reality of public schools in the municipality of São Raimundo Nonato, in the state of Piauí. Analyzing the results, parents and guardians play an important role in the psychological development of their children, from early childhood to the end of adolescence, and their importance in monitoring and supporting school development is indispensable for the formation and enhancement of students' human and psychological development. Considering the data, it is evident that almost half of the students responded that their parents or guardians are absent in participating in and monitoring their children's school development, which explains the large percentage of students who suffer from psychological problems at school.

The data also showed that 76.40% of the students interviewed feel comfortable talking about bullying at school and with their families. Regarding being a victim of bullying at their current school, the majority of students, 64%, say they have suffered some type of bullying. See the results in Figures 02, 03, and 04.

Figure 02: Types of bullying suffered by students at school

The figure shows the types of bullying, with verbal bullying being the most prevalent, followed by psychological bullying, moral or emotional bullying, and material bullying. It is important to note that the group of students did not report any incidents of cyberbullying or sexual bullying. When asked if they had told anyone at school that they had been bullied, 64.92% said yes, and 35.08% said no. According to Smith and Sharp (1995 apud MELO, 2022, p. 2),

Direct bullying, both physical and verbal, includes physical aggression, sexual abuse, theft or damage to another person's property, extortion, insults, name-calling, and racist comments. Indirect bullying, on the other hand, includes excluding a person from the group, gossiping and name-calling that marginalizes others, and any other type of manipulation committed by an individual or group against another.

Given that one of the biggest psychological problems developed in adolescence arises from conflictual coexistence in the school environment, coupled with a lack of communication with family or guardians, victims of bullying often remain silent, suffering alone in a situation that is social in nature and needs to be resolved.

Figure 03: People who are aware of bullying suffered by students at school

It should be noted that most students have already told a friend that they have been bullied, which contrasts with the small number of students who tell their closest relative, whether maternal or paternal. It is important that public schools provide a comfortable, ethical, and moral environment with the periodic presence of psychologists, educators, and social workers to welcome troubled students and intervene in reality.

The previous data confirmed that most students responded that they feel comfortable talking about the subject both at school and at home, a positive point in this research that needs to be reflected upon and considered from a philosophical perspective, in line with Freire's (2014) emancipatory and liberating education. Since the educational process takes place in communion between individuals, the teacher must have the sensitivity to perceive and identify students who are facing bullying.

Figure 04: Student reaction to a situation of bullying at school

The graph shows, based on the students' responses, that the majority defend the victim (79.78% of respondents) and none of the students get involved in helping with the aggression. This reality reveals the search for a culture of peace in schools, which these new generations are capable of adhering to, and in this context, the school has an important role to play in promoting educational actions that lead to this culture of peace. Therefore, analyzing the results obtained, it can be inferred that the main means of minimizing, if not ending, this practice is dialogue. Awareness leads each party to understand their importance in this discussion, their opinions and perceptions, whether they are teachers, parents, or students.

1.1.2 Pedagogical axis: CEEP-Gercílio de Castro Macêdo

At the CEEP-Gercílio de Castro Macêdo school, 385 students were surveyed using a questionnaire designed to identify the number of students who had been victims of or witnessed bullying in the school environment. The survey revealed the extent to which this practice is present among students at the school, with many suffering from it and others engaging in it. After the survey, a lecture was held at the school on the topic, which highlighted the importance of addressing this issue in schools, as bullying can cause irreparable damage to students' lives.

The students interviewed were aged between 14 and 22 years old and were in the 1st, 2nd, and 3rd years of high school. The survey results showed that at the CEEP-Gercílio de Castro Macêdo public school in the municipality of São Raimundo Nonato, male students predominate, accounting for 58% of the student body, while female students accounted for 42% of the respondents. When asked if they had ever been bullied in public schools, 55% of students confirmed that they had, while 13% said they had not and 32% did not respond. The following figure shows the occurrence of bullying in the institution investigated.

Figure 05: Rates of bullying cases in school

From the above, it can be seen that 29% of students have been bullied at school, with 29% suffering frequently and 59% rarely, but still suffering nonetheless. Meanwhile, 3% of respondents said they experience this situation every day. When asked to report any cases they had suffered or witnessed, the responses focused on reasons such as physical appearance, hair, and body. Many also said they had been bullied at their former schools, which included physical, emotional, and psychological aggression, such as nicknames that caused discomfort. When asked what can happen to the victim if these practices are recurrent, the responses were: depression, isolation, learning difficulties, poor performance in class, and even suicide. Of those who said they had experienced bullying and did not tell their parents out of shame, 60% responded that they feel ashamed to talk about it with their parents, while 37% responded that they had already reported it to a family member and 3% preferred not to answer the question. Regarding bullying at school, the majority, 60%, responded no, while 40% responded yes. According to Silva and Oliveira (2019), adolescence is a period of many intense biological, social, and psychological changes and of defining the identity of adolescents, and should be considered an essential stage of human development. Conflictual situations between adolescents and between adolescents and adults that lead to exclusion, humiliation, and personal and academic failure as a result of aggression stemming from bullying contribute to students questioning their social role, their abilities, and their own level of importance. In addition, this process can lead to decreased self-esteem and suicidal ideation, which can be avoided as long as attention is paid to true importance be given to this subject in schools.

1.1.3 Pedagogical axis: Edith Nobre de Castro School Unit

As Barbosa et al (2016) state, the implications of bullying on self-esteem and pressures in the victim's personal life can lead to suicide, as it is a complex phenomenon determined by several factors. Adolescents in crisis find themselves in the midst of a struggle between themselves and the social environment in which they live, and if

If this balance between the two is altered, death would be the only way out for many. Suicide among young people around the world is increasing, so the lecture series was important as a space for dialogue between education professionals and students, identifying situations and proposing ways to deal with them, based on discussion of the subject.

After the lecture series, the Program's scholarship recipients conducted quantitative research by collecting and systematizing data through questionnaires and an essay related to the subject at school and family participation in the school environment, applied at the Edith Nobre de Castro school during the morning shift in the 1st, 2nd, and 3rd years of high school, with the authorization of the school's general management and teachers. Below, we present all the diagnostic results obtained at the school for questionnaires Q2 to Q12, according to the graphical representations (Figs. 6, 7, and 8).

Figure 06: Gender and age group of students who experienced bullying at school

Figure 7: Number of bullying situations experienced by high school students

Figure 8: Number of bullying situations experienced by high school students

These data suggest that male students have already suffered bullying in their school environment, in the public education system of the municipality of São Raimundo Nonato. More pronounced results were found in question Q4 for female students who responded that they had been bullied, exceeding 30%, which is 20% higher than male students. In summary, the results presented in Figs. 7 and 8 show that this phenomenon is a reality in the lives of students in public schools in the municipality, where approximately 100% of students are aware of the situations, with 40% of students reporting having been bullied, 17% stating that they have witnessed some type of bullying, and 95% of the students interviewed having participated in lectures on the subject.

Almost half of the students who responded to the questionnaires said they had a good family life, with most recognizing the importance of good family relations and participating in their children's school life. Few reported that their parents do not participate in their children's school life. In the questionnaire, students also reported that family events interfere with their school performance, which is a worrying result and requires intervention in reality, where managers, together with psychological and social assistance from public schools in the municipality, must be aware of this situation.

Given this reality, solutions to the problem of bullying, which is common not only in the municipality's public schools but across the globe, can be minimized by establishing educational models designed jointly by municipal, state, and federal education systems. It is necessary to enable and develop projects with policies for continuing education and intervention in public schools, creating and developing projects and laws aimed at the permanence of psychology, social assistance, dental care, interdisciplinary practices, and theatrical performances as a means of mediation between students, so that they can get to know each other better and interact through sports, participation in academic and sports competitions, improvement of school buildings and library collections, and properly air-conditioned environments in public schools in the municipality of São Raimundo Nonato.

Still on the subject of PIBID activities in schools, it is worth highlighting the interdisciplinary activities (science fairs) organized by school administrators and teachers

and students from the Physics Degree course at IFPI/CASRN. According to Neves and Gonçalves (1989), science fairs in Brazil and abroad have increasingly demonstrated important alternatives for encouraging and stimulating students and teachers in the search for new knowledge, offering themselves as a significant space for scientific initiation, production, and socialization of knowledge.

2 Results and discussion

The municipality of São Raimundo Nonato, whose inhabitants are called São Raimundenses (area of 2,415.287 ^{km}²), has a population density of 13.38 inhabitants per km², with a Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and per capita income of R\$ 12,993.94, according to the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE) census (2018/2010) 3. It has 34,877 inhabitants, with 98% of the population aged between 6 and 14 years old. However, with a low human development index averaging 0.661 (income, education, and health), the survey conducted by the IBGE shows an underdeveloped city that needs public municipal development actions, especially in the city's municipal schools.

As already explained, the PIBID developed by scholarship students and a physics teacher from IFPI in the municipality focused on politicizing teacher training and valorization, honoring in its commitments the social, political, and ethical project of the students of the Physics Degree course at *the São Raimundo Nonato Campus*. Based on the actions developed by the PIBID/IFPI/CASRN team, the results are consistent with the studies by Massena and Siqueira (2016) that the Program can contribute to the improvement of both the "school space" and the training of future teachers.

Thus, after the technical visits, during the term of the PIBID/IFPI/CASRN scholarship, the students presented the various issues in discursive results, with the intention of instigating interventions and public policies aimed at improving relations in the school environment. In the field diary, the students reported on the various issues, with the intention of instigating interventions and public policies aimed at improving relations in the school environment. the scholarship recipients presented discursive results on various issues, with the intention of instigating interventions and public policies aimed at improving relationships in the school environment. In their field diaries, the students reported a lack of public policies for school support and maintenance, such as defects in the structural buildings of the schools (floors, walls), inappropriate recreation areas, auditoriums without useful materials for developing self-knowledge, expression, and communication among students, lack of science and computer labs, libraries with outdated collections, damaged and unused air conditioning equipment in public schools in the municipality of São Raimundo Nonato. It can be inferred that a possible solution to alleviate and improve the school environment would be to seek public policies, through the dissemination and presentation to public managers of reports and projects that contribute to the improvement of educational institutions.

Based on discussions held throughout the Program's activities on school facilities and their importance in the teaching and learning process, where public policies are fundamental to improving the quality of school facilities, it is of utmost importance and fundamental to train new generations of professionals who will occupy social positions and thus serve the population, and then build a path for national progress with order and progress not only in the municipal schools of São Raimundo Nonato, but in all public entities that educate young people in Brazil.

Observations of the reality of public schools in São Raimundo (school space in its physical structure and pedagogical organization) were developed through diagnostic research for the purpose of observing the cognitive psychological construction of students in the municipality's public schools, where motivational and explanatory lectures on bullying were given, since "the prevention of *bullying* among students constitutes

a necessary public health measure, capable of enabling the full development of children and adolescents, enabling them to enjoy healthy and safe social interaction." (NETO, 2005, p. 164).

Bullying refers to a situation of continuous, repetitive aggression, with characteristics of persecution of the victim by the aggressor, which is increasingly present in the school environment in public schools and has become one of the main concerns of teachers and school administrators who frequently witness this violence among students.

Although bullying occurs in the context of educational institutions, it is not only a problem for schools, but for society as a whole, as it is a phenomenon that generates long-term problems, causing serious damage to the psyche and negatively interfering with the cognitive, emotional, and socio-educational development of those involved (FANTE, 2008a apud FREIRE; AIRES, 2012, p. 56).

Based on the experiences already reported, it is considered that PIBID provided scholarship students in the Physics degree program with the opportunity to learn about the pedagogical dynamics and social interactions of the educational context, their future work environment, where they placed themselves in the position of teachers, assisting basic education professionals and more experienced teachers in the search for educational actions aimed at improving teaching and learning processes.

Certain that "the reality of everyday life is shared with others" (BERGER; LUCKMANN, 2004, p. 46), the interaction between teachers, students, and scholarship recipients in the Program provided experiences at school that allowed them not only to observe the school environment, but also to develop activities that contributed to a more humane education. In this perspective, one of the main activities developed within the school unit was a lecture on bullying given by the director of education of the IFPI and the coordinator of the PIBID/IFPI/CASRN Area.

It is well known that bullying is a form of symbolic violence practiced in the school environment, manifested in verbal, physical, and psychological aggression, among others, based on prejudice and discrimination against others, in which an individual or group considers itself superior or better than another person, thus exercising a "power" of domination. In this relationship, the dominated person who suffers this symbolic violence "[...] has only the instruments of knowledge that they have in common with the dominant person, which makes this relationship seem natural" (BOURDIEU, 1997, p. 204). Thus, all PIBID lectures that took place in the pedagogical axes CEEP-Gercílio de Castro Macêdo, Centro de Ensino Médio de Tempo Integral Moderna-CETI, and Unidade Escolar Edith Nobre de Castro were focused on the problems caused by bullying in the educational environment.

Final Considerations

In view of the above, we recognize that PIBID at IFPI *Campus* São Raimundo Nonato deserves recognition and a continued policy of incentives, starting with national authorities in the dissemination and development of projects and proposals in innovative lines of perspective, offered by the Coordination for the Improvement of Higher Education Personnel (CAPES). The experiences at the Centro de Ensino Médio de Tempo Integral Moderna (CETI), CEEP-Gercílio de Castro Macêdo, and Unidade Escolar Edith Nobre de Castro schools reflect an important and renewed concern with teaching practice.

PIBID, as a public policy, was very important in the construction and consolidation of reflections in the various activities developed by the scholarship recipients, such as qualitative and quantitative diagnostic research procedures, offering a new epistemology in the initial training of teachers. In addition, the pedagogical experiences of the teacher trainees in scientific seminar cycles were successful and served to promote understanding of the teaching profession, attributing ethical and moral values to teaching work in public schools in the municipality of São Raimundo Nonato, in Piauí.

The observations and reflections on the school environment from the pedagogical axes chosen by PIBID/CAPES showed the reality of students in public schools in the municipality of São Raimundo Nonato, as a fundamental part of the research on professional improvement of Physics graduates from IFPI/CASRN. This made it possible to investigate and realize that the school is associated with the democratic management of public actions that favor future professionals who will assume social positions. The PIBID/IFPI/CASRN team clarified with the pedagogical axis directors of the municipality's public schools that it is important to develop innovative projects and seek their rights from municipal administrations to improve the quality of teaching and learning for students, as well as to seek support for projects and proposals to be implemented in public schools.

The program enabled students enrolled in the Physics Degree program to act as teacher-researchers, sharing their training experiences and obtaining positive gains in terms of valuing teaching from constructive academic perspectives, reframed for the quality of basic education and the initial training of teachers themselves.

We hope that these experiences will serve as an incentive and model for other public schools to understand the reality of public school teaching centers through interdisciplinary activities, already discussed and presented, and innovative project actions that contribute to the teaching and learning process of future physics teachers.

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